

Factors that Influenced and Problems Encountered in the Criminologist Licensure Examination

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Abstract:- The results of the Criminologist Licensure Examination are indeed a significant indicator of student performance in the Bachelor of Science in Criminology. This study aimed to determine the extent of factors that influenced and degree of seriousness of problems encountered in preparing and taking the licensure examination as perceived by CLE passers and Criminology faculty of two higher education institutions in the province of Antique, Philippines. A descriptive research design was used to analyze and interpret the data. Results of the study revealed that several factors such as student, home and family, school, review center and personal have high influence on the licensure examination performance. In addition, there is no significant difference in the respondents' perception of the different factors that influence the performance in CLE. Regarding the degree of seriousness of problems encountered in preparing and taking the CLE, the respondents perceived these problems as serious. It was also revealed that there is a significant correlation between problems encountered and the following factors: student factor, home and family factor, school factor, and personal factor. Meanwhile, no significant correlation exists between problems encountered and review center factor. The findings of this study may serve as a basis for making policies and initiating programs that will improve the students' performance and success in the licensure examination.

Keywords:- Criminology, factors, licensure examination, performance, problems.

I. INTRODUCTION

The licensure examination is critical in determining a school's performance in terms of the quality of education it provides. This examination is a necessity for practicing a particular profession. It is a prerequisite to becoming a recognized expert in one's specific discipline (Binayao and Dales, 2020). Actual results in the Philippine Criminologist Licensure Examination are the best indicator of student performance in the Bachelor of Science in Criminology Program. The knowledge, skills and competencies that are stated to be the likely outputs of a quality-assured HEI (Padua, 2012) could be measured to some extent through these assessments.

This criterion applies to all criminology education in the country. It's worth noting that, as far as we know, criminology graduates are only required to pass the criminologist licensure test (CLE) before they can be recognized as "criminologists" in the Philippines (Barrera,

Cagang & Capistrano, 2013). This licensure examination is required by Republic Act No. 11131, also known as "The Philippine Criminology Profession Act of 2018," which states that anyone who wants to practice criminology should pass the Professional Regulation Commission's (PRC) Professional Regulatory Board of Criminology's Criminologists Licensure Examinations (CLE).

The mission of the criminology program, according to CMO No. 5 series of 2018, is to provide the community with professionally competent and morally upright graduates who can provide efficient and effective services in crime prevention, crime detection and investigation, law enforcement, public safety, custody and rehabilitation of offenders, and criminological research. In addition, the program envisions educational institutions being actively and continuously involved in producing graduates with the knowledge, skills, attitude, and values necessary to address the country's criminality problems, as well as the character and competence necessary to meet the challenges of globalization in the area of criminology. All Higher Education Institutions offer this program in the hopes of responding to the community's needs and interests.

From board examinations for criminologists in 2018, 2019, and 2021, the Philippines has produced 60,430 licensed criminologists out of 161,527 examinees with an average national passing percentage of 36.95% (PRC, 2018a; PRC, 2018b; PRC, 2019a; PRC, 2019b; PRC, 2021). In particular, Region VI, which includes the provinces of Aklan, Antique, Capiz, Iloilo, Guimaras, and Negros Occidental, produced 4,489 out of 15,086 test-takers, with a regional passing percentage of 29.41%. In the testing periods from 2018, 2019, and 2021, the province of Antique produced a total of 322 licensed criminologists out of 1,312 takers, with a provincial passing rate of 27.04 %.

In other disciplines, there is a considerable amount of research exploring the variables that predict licensure examination performance. However, there is a dearth of research in the Philippines that identifies the predictors of performance on the Criminologist Licensure Examination or merely examines the performance of higher education institutions on the CLE. The CLE performance of each State University and College (SUC) is one of the elements for quality assurance as a center of development and excellence, and it may also significantly influence the performance of each university.

As a result, criminology graduates from HEIs in Antique are now confronted with the challenge of developing globally competitive graduates, particularly those who will take the board exams. The researcher was encouraged to conduct this study after becoming aware of the various factors that influenced and problems encountered in the licensure examination. The study sought to determine the extent of factors that influenced and the degree of seriousness of problems encountered in the CLE as perceived by CLE passers and criminology faculty.

This study is believed to be useful for school administrators, faculty, criminology students, and criminology graduates who will take the CLE of Higher Education Institutions in the Philippines in terms of the factors that influence and problems encountered in passing the CLE, which is the focus of this study. Administrators will also be assisted in developing policies that will increase the school's performance on the licensure exam. It could also be the most ideal means for curriculum developers, school administrators, teachers, criminology students, and graduates to take a step forward in strengthening criminologists' professional competence and the criminology profession in the country.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to one study, the home and family factors have a strong influence on CLE achievement, whereas the other factors namely: student, school, review center, and personal indicators have an average influence only (Albina, Balasabas, Laquinon, Pampilo & Caballero, 2022). Furthermore, ten theme clusters emerged as factors influencing CLE success. The following are the factors: (1) program interest and focus, (2) undisrupted schooling, (3) moral and financial support from parents, (4) sufficiency of classrooms, laboratory equipment, and physical facilities, (5) availability of qualified and committed faculty, (6) use of various teaching methodologies that encourage effective learning, (7) a cut-off grade-based retention policy (8) attendance at review centers on a regular basis (9) sufficient time, focus, and discipline during the review period, and lastly (10) the ability to manage test anxiety and retain what has been studied.

In terms of the student-related factor, Refugio (2019) discovered that HEIs in Abra screened incoming teacher education enrollees. Before awarding completion certificates in their course, the graduate students were scrutinized, and they honed teacher aspirants to become catalysts for change and molders of youth. College admission examinations may also play a significant role in student-related factors. In the selection process, interviewers such as college deans, program heads and teacher education faculty should evaluate student applicants' verbal understanding, figural reasoning, and quantitative skills.

Another significant study was that of Agboola et al. (2014), who asserted that the university admission process

is crucial. Admission information has historically been used as a predictive factor of success by most educational systems, and when assessed, it may help determine students who are at risk of low academic performance, as well as play a part in the indicators that may likely predict the quality of students but not predict low performance. Student quality, on the other hand, is a factor of the forces that shape students' qualities such as academic performance, study, coping mechanisms, course satisfaction, and ability to persevere in the educational system. It is a key indicator of an institution's efficiency.

Barrera et al. (2013) discovered that the main subject GPA and English Qualifying Examination results were found to predict performance in the CLE in the Philippines. Meanwhile, the research findings of Badua (2020) disclosed that their criminology graduates perform moderately well academically and have a passing average in the CLE. Furthermore, respondents of her study reported that poor student study habits, poor faculty instruction, poor review class management, and financial and health issues were experienced from school, review, and board examination.

Moreover, according to Albina et al. (2022), interest in and focus on one's course while still in college is a significant factor that influences licensure exam performance when graduates decide to take the exam later on. Some participants in this study disclosed that they very often attended classes due to a lack of interest or of peer pressure. This finding was consistent with that of Kwi-Soon and Bok-Sun (2009), whose respondents expressed remorse for not studying harder while in nursing school. According to Tan (2014), "one predictor that has a strong correlation with licensure examination performance is the attitude of students towards their studies."

In Ventayen's (2020) study, factors associated with faculty-related predictors revealed that it is also an indicator of LET performance. Faculty members must be equipped with knowledge, skills, and values which can be used to produce dynamic and high-quality educators in the field of teacher education. This finding was also supported by Gurney (2007), who also asserted that faculty members with high levels of qualification and training help to improve standards in educational institutions.

Respondents in Villarmia (2017)'s study also indicated that the "first two years of the degree (B.S. Criminology) was frustrating. It was during these years that all of their instructors handling major subjects were part-time instructors. These instructors did not focus on teaching and usually made absences because they were police personnel and private lawyer." This supports Dayaday's (2018) research findings, which claimed that faculty and instructional materials have a positive influence on test-takers' performance.

Moreover, "grades should ideally reflect students' mastery of course competencies. As a result, mandating a cut-off grade for professional courses as a basis for student retention in a specific academic program is

necessary.”This is another theme revealed in the study of Albina et al. (2022), which lends support to the Lawson and Till (2006) study, which confirmed that students should continue their education only after demonstrating a level of mastery.

In terms of the school-related factor, Villarmia (2017) discovered that “only used a few criminology types of equipment and experienced incomplete laboratory activities in their subjects”. Similarly, Dayaday (2018) asserted that lack of laboratory equipment contributed to the examinees' poor performance. Furthermore, this study confirms the findings of Albina et al. (2022) that “adequate laboratory equipment is required to promote effective and experiential learning in students.”

A similar study on quality education and practice innovation instruction to improve graduate performance has been conducted by Quiambao (2015). The study's findings revealed that student, teacher, and school factors may indeed contribute to a higher probability of passing the LET. Academic performance is strongly related to LET performance. The findings are consistent with those of a related study, which found a positive relationship between the results of the CPA board examination and students' academic performance. Several authors, such as Arcilla and Apare (2018), agree with previous studies' findings. The notion supports the claim that academic performance has a great influence on licensure examinations.

Kwi-Soon and Bok-Sun (2009) discovered that the support of participants' families and those around them motivated those who were hesitant to make preparations for the examination (NCLEX-RN) because of a lack of self-confidence. This study backs up the findings of Albina et al (2022) that “parental support both in financial and moral aspects makes a significant difference in exam performance.”

According to the study by Albina et al. (2022), “regular attendance at review sessions offered by review centers is also a contributory factor that increases the chances of passing the CLE.” This idea is supported by Kwi-Soon and Bok-Sun's (2009) study, which found that “taking the preparation course resulted in improvement in participants' English reading abilities and consolidation of their knowledge.” Similarly, Lascano and Bansiong (2017) recognized that “attendance at review classes can increase one's chances of passing exams.” Furthermore, Herrero (2015) highlighted the importance of university and review school-administered pre-board or mock board exams. She also noticed that review centers have current review resources.

Moreover, Pariñas and Obrero (2012) investigated the significance of the topics tackled in the review program in relation to the respondents' profile, such as age, year graduated, sex, UNP CAT rating, number of taken examinations, and civil status, as well as the level of relevance of the subjects lectured during reviews and the

problems encountered in the various areas of concentrations in the Criminology Licensure Examination.

Another study of teacher education graduates found that graduates plan to do a variety of things after graduation, including looking for work. However, the majority of graduates intended to take the LET as soon as possible. Graduates typically prepare by enrolling in a review center, but a few opted for self-review due to financial struggles and time constraints (Aquino and Ballila, 2015). Every graduate's eagerness to pass the licensure examination is admirable, but according to some studies, review factors are influencing the results.

Albina et al. (2022) discovered that one of the challenges faced by CLE non-passers is indeed a lack of exam preparation due to one's employment. This finding backs up the findings of Kwi-Soon and Bok-Sun (2009), who found that if participants were too busy to study, they would consider quitting. Work-related exhaustion, both physically and mentally, reduced motivation to study.

Additionally, Kwi-Soon and Bok-Sun (2009) noted in their study that “some participants who failed on the first try were ashamed of the failure that they wanted to hide themselves”. This is also supportive of what Albina et al. (2022) which concluded in their study that personal and social consequences of failing the exam placed so much pressure on the participants to the extent that they felt ashamed to go home or they would have low self-esteem if they did not pass the exam.

According to Villarmia (2017), respondents' (B.S. Criminology graduating students) knowledge is insufficient, particularly for subjects studied during their first and second years. This supports the findings of Albina et al (2022), which found that answering the licensure exam was a major challenge for many participants because some topics were not covered in school. This is due, in part, to a lack of regular faculty members who could teach specific major courses.

According to the findings of Kwi-Soon and Bok-Sun (2009), a studious environment was created at home for participants who had children. This contradicts the findings of the study of Albina et al (2022), which found that family responsibilities, along with parental responsibilities, are among the factors influencing examinees CLE results. Such that, some participants are burdened by responsibilities to their families and children.

Furthermore, Albina et al. (2022) discovered that critical thinking and analyzing every item on the exam is one of the key factors affecting exam performance. This finding supports the findings of Kaddoura et al. (2017), who discovered a statistically significant relationship between critical thinking scores and NCLEX-RN passing rates. Significant relationships were discovered between respondents' grades (whether or not they had a failing grade in one of their professional courses) and the factors that influenced CLE success, as well as between grades and the difficulties associated with preparing for and taking the CLE. Amanonce and Maramag (2020) revealed

a similar and significant correlation between graduates' grade weighted average in college and performance on the Licensure Examination for Teachers in their study. The same strong relationship was discovered between professional course grades and test-takers ratings on the professional subtest in licensure examinations (Alhifany et al., 2020).

The previous literature and studies have provided insights into the current study. It provided the researcher with a clear understanding of the various contributing factors that affected licensure examination performance. It also discloses some issues encountered while preparing for and taking the CLE. Lastly, several related studies were cited that may confirm or refute the current study's findings.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The descriptive research method was used in this study because it was appropriate for the problem. This method entails gathering data in order to answer questions about the phenomenon's current status or trend (Gay, 2012). The method used in this study investigated the extent of factors that influenced and the degree of seriousness of problems encountered in the Criminologist Licensure Examination as perceived by CLE passers and criminology faculty.

The survey and correlational descriptive research designs were used. The survey design was used to evaluate student, home and family, school, review center, and personal factors that may influence CLE performance, as well as perceptions of problems associated with preparing for and taking the CLE. In contrast, the correlational design investigated the relationship between factors that influenced and the seriousness of problems encountered in the CLE.

B. Population and Locale of the Study

The study has two groups of respondents. For the first group of respondents, it includes graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Criminology programs at the University of Antique in Sibalom, Antique, and St. Anthony's College in San Jose, Antique who took and passed the CLE administered by the Board of Criminology of the Professional Regulation Commission during the testing periods of December 2018, November 2019, and December 2021. Stratified proportional sampling was used to select the graduates as survey respondents. According to Hayes (2021), "stratified random sampling ensures that each subgroup of a given population is adequately represented within a research study's overall sample population." In a proportionate stratified method, the sample size for each stratum is proportional to the stratum's population size. The second group of respondents included all criminology faculty members from the University of Antique and St. Anthony's College, regardless of appointment status.

Category	Respondent Population		No. of survey respondents	%
CLE Passers				
University of Antique	172	103	59.88	
St. Anthony's College	41	27	65.85	
Total	213	130	61.03	
Criminology Faculty				
University of Antique	19	19	100	
St. Anthony's College	13	12	93.31	
Total	32	31	96.88	
Total No. of Respondents	245	161	65.71	

Table 1: Population of the Study

C. Research Instrument

The data gathering instrument used in this study is a four-page questionnaire adapted from the study of Albina et al. (2022), and the study titled "Factors and Challenges Influencing the Criminologist Licensure Examination Performance Through the Non-passers Lens." Part 1 elicits demographic information about the respondents,

including their group as CLE passer and criminology faculty. Part 2 evaluates the extent of agreement on CLE-influencing factors such as student factors, home and family factors, school factors, review center factors, and personal factors. Two items were added to this section of the questionnaire based on the themes identified in the Albina et al (2022) study, one on student factor written

as "Focus in the course (B.S. Criminology)" and one on problems encountered written as "I have problems with the examination venue and accommodation." Part 3 of the instrument addressed issues related to preparing for and taking the CLE. Based on extensive readings of relevant literature, ten items were added to the questionnaire.

The instrument was pilot tested to 30 CLE passers and 24 criminology faculty of other criminology schools in Western Visayas. The internal consistency (Cronbach's Alpha) of the whole 40-item instrument revealed an excellent reliability (Cronbach's Alpha = .92). Investigating the categories of the instrument: for the category of a student factor has good and acceptable reliability (Cronbach's Alpha = .73), for home and family factor has good reliability (Cronbach's Alpha = .81), for school factor has good reliability (Cronbach's Alpha = .85), for review center factor has acceptable reliability (Cronbach's Alpha = .69), for personal factor has good reliability (Cronbach's Alpha = .85), and for problems encountered has excellent reliability (Cronbach's Alpha = .93).

D. Data Gathering Procedure

Permission was obtained from the Office of the Dean, College of Arts and Sciences, University of Antique, Sibalom, Antique, and the Office of the College President, St. Anthony's College, San Jose, Antique, to

To interpret the perception of respondents in regards to the factors that influenced the CLE, the following scale of means was used:

Response	Scale	Interpretation
4	3.26-4.00	High Influence
3	2.51-3.25	Average Influence
2	1.76-2.50	Low Influence
1	1.00-1.75	Least Influence

To interpret the perception of respondents in regards to the degree of seriousness of problems encountered in the CLE, the following scale of means was used:

Response	Scale	Interpretation
4	3.26-4.00	Very Serious
3	2.51-3.25	Serious
2	1.76-2.50	Moderately Serious
1	1.00-1.75	Less Serious

Meanwhile, the Mann-Whitney U-test was used to ascertain the significance of the difference in the extent of factors that influenced and degree of seriousness of problems encountered in CLE. Lastly, Spearman's Rho test was employed to ascertain the correlation between the extent of factors that influenced and the degree of seriousness of problems encountered in CLE.

F. Ethical Considerations

The informed consent that vouched for the voluntary nature of their participation ensured the confidentiality and privacy of the information provided by the respondent. This guaranteed that all information pertaining to respondents' identities would be kept

conduct the study. After obtaining the necessary permit, the researcher communicated with the respondents about their availability via social media and phone calls.

The data was collected between March 15 to April 10, 2022. The researcher used Google Forms to create a web-based survey and distributed the link via emails and private messages. Only responses from those who completed the form and met the criteria of being a CLE passer and criminology faculty at the University of Antique and St. Anthony's College were accepted. Finally, after gathering the required number of respondents, the collected data were tabulated and analyzed using various statistical treatments.

E. Statistical Treatment

The statistician used IBM - Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) to analyze the data collected from the Google forms. The descriptive statistical treatment was also used to analyze the mean and standard deviation. The standard deviation was used to determine the respondents' homogeneity and heterogeneity in terms of their perception of the factors that influenced and problems encountered in the CLE, while the weighted mean was used to determine the extent of influence of different factors and the degree of seriousness of problems encountered in the CLE. The weighted mean was further interpreted using the 4-point Likert scale as follows:

private and not revealed to anyone. Furthermore, their availability and willingness to participate in the study were taken into account. Respondents were also informed that they could withdraw from the study at any time and that they could be replaced by another willing and available respondent. Finally, there is no monetary compensation, reward, or promise made to the respondents in this study. The information provided by respondents is not accessible to anyone other than the researcher. All responses were saved in the researcher's password-protected database. All information pertaining to this study is solely for the development of the study and is not for the pursuit of any individual.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Extent of Influence of the Different Factors in the CLE Performance as Perceived by the Respondents

Factors	Mean	SD	D
Student Factor			
1.Interest in the course (B.S. Criminology)	3.78	.483	HI
2.Time spent on studying lessons	3.55	.611	HI
3.Doing research in the library or through internet	3.24	.687	AI
4.Number of hours spent reading books and materials	3.29	.658	HI
5.Focus in the course (B.S. Criminology)	3.75	.513	HI
Grand Mean	3.52	.438	HI
Home and Family Factor			
6.Family gives motivation and encouragement	3.65	.606	HI
7.Family supports all expenses in reviewing and taking the CLE	3.70	.600	HI
8.Parents help a lot in preparations for the CLE	3.45	.724	HI
9.Family can be depended upon when a problem arises	3.40	.745	HI
Grand Mean	3.55	.536	HI
School Factor			
10.Availability of qualified and dedicated faculty and staff	3.58	.597	HI
11.Teaching strategies used by instructors that promote effective learning	3.71	.505	HI
12.Adequacy of classrooms with proper ventilation	3.40	.710	HI
13.Easy access to transportation going to school	3.31	.768	HI
14.Adequacy of audio-visual resources	3.44	.650	HI
15.Adequacy of laboratory equipment and physical facilities	3.35	.728	HI
Grand Mean	3.47	.503	HI
Review Center Factor			
16.Regular attendance to review sessions/classes conducted by the review center	3.58	.695	HI
17.Active participation in the review sessions/classes conducted by the review center	3.57	.705	HI
Grand Mean	3.57	.655	HI
Personal Factor			
18.High motivation to pass the licensure exam	3.83	.412	HI
19.Ability to think critically and analyze every item in the exam	3.73	.471	HI
20.Emotionally stable when taking the exam	3.66	.536	HI
21.Ability to manage test anxiety and other negative emotions	3.64	.531	HI
22.Ability to retain what has been memorized	3.47	.689	HI
Grand Mean	3.67	.419	HI

Table 2: Extent of Influence of the Different Factors in the CLE Performance as Perceived by the Respondents

Legend: High influence= 3.26-4.00, Average influence= 2.51-3.25, Low Influence= 1.76-2.50, Least Influence= 1.00-1.75

As revealed by the data presented in table 2, the respondents perceived high influence in the CLE performance among the different factors considered in this study namely: student factor (M=3.52, SD=.438), home and family factor (M=3.55, SD=.536), school factor (M=3.47, SD=.503), review center factor (M=3.57, SD=.655) and personal factor (M=3.67, SD=.419). This implies that the respondents recognized that all five factors have a great impact on the performance in the licensure examination.

It can also be noted in table 2, that out of the 22 pre-listed factors, 21 of them were perceived by the respondents to have a high influence on CLE performance. One item from student factor, specifically “doing research in the library or through internet” was perceived to have an average influence on the CLE performance as reflected in its weighted mean of 3.24

(SD=.687). This confirms the result of the study of Albina et al. (2022) which likewise revealed that the same item in student factor was perceived to have average influence among the non-passers in the CLE.

Similarly, the findings in this study support other findings in the Albina et al. (2022) study, which also revealed that home and family factors have a high influence on CLE performance. The remaining factors, namely the student factor, school factor, review center factor, and personal factor, have a moderate influence on licensure exam performance. Furthermore, the findings of this study support Herrero's (2015) study, which found that home and family factors, as well as student factors, have a significant impact on CPA exam performance.

Furthermore, the findings of this study revealed that the adequacy of laboratory equipment and physical

facilities are regarded as important factors influencing graduate performance in licensure examinations. Schools, according to Alimini (2004), were established for the purpose of teaching and learning. To facilitate the teaching and learning process, it is critical that teachers and students are properly accommodated. Likewise, Bandele (2003) emphasized the significance of physical facilities, which cannot be overlooked. Modern laboratories, libraries, and classrooms are to be installed in all of our schools.

Except for the home and family factor, these findings concur with Serrano's (2000) findings, which revealed that “review school attended, school, peers and review mates (not included in this study), individual/personal skills, and in-house review program (not also included in this study) are factors that affect licensure examination performance as perceived by those who successfully passed the licensure examination.”

Difference in the Extent of Influence of the Different Factors in the CLE as Perceived by the Respondents

Factors in the CLE	Mean Rank	u-value	p-value	Interpretation
Student factor				
CLE Passer	78.03	2,401.000	.093	Not Significant
Criminology faculty	93.45			
Home and Family factor				
CLE Passer	80.17	2,123.500	.627	Not Significant
Criminology faculty	84.50			
School factor				
CLE Passer	79.81	2,169.500	.503	Not Significant
Criminology faculty	85.98			
Review Center factor				
CLE Passer	81.20	1,989.500	.902	Not Significant
Criminology faculty	80.18			
Personal factor				
CLE Passer	79.54	2,205.000	.392	Not Significant
Criminology faculty	87.13			

Table 3: Difference in the Extent of Influence of the Different Factors in the CLE as Perceived by the Respondents

* – significant ($p < .05$)
 ** – not significant ($p > .05$)

Mann-Whitney U Test results in Table 3 revealed that as to student factor, no significant difference was noted as shown by the u-value of 2,401.000 with a p-value of .093 which was greater than the set 0.05 level of significance.

Moreover, as to home and family factor, it can be inferred in the table that no significant difference was noted as shown by the computed u-value of 2,123.500 with a p-value of .627 which was greater than the set 0.05 level of significance.

On the other hand, as to school factor, no significant difference was noted as shown by the u-value of 2,169.5000 with a p-value of 0.503 which was greater than the set 0.05 level of significance.

Meanwhile, as to review center factor, it can be

inferred that the no significant difference was noted as shown by the u-value of 1,989.500 with a p-value of .902 which was greater than the set 0.05 level of significance.

Finally, as to personal factor, no significant difference was noted as shown by the u-value of 2,205.000 with a p-value of .392 which was greater than the set 0.05 level of significance.

The results imply that the respondents have similar perceptions as regards to the different factors that influence the performance in CLE. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that “there is no significant difference in the extent of influence of the different factors as perceived by the respondents” is not rejected, meaning, the perceptions of the two groups do not significantly differ.

Degree of Seriousness of Problems Encountered in the CLE as Perceived by the Respondents

Problems	Mean	SD	Description
1. The exam is very difficult to answer.	3.09	.762	Serious
2. Some items in the exam were not discussed in school.	3.08	.806	Serious

3.Unfamiliarity with some of the words used in the exam items.	3.06	.756	Serious
4.Personal pressures of passing the exam.	3.14	.810	Serious
5. Social pressures of passing the exam.	3.17	.760	Serious
6. Family pressures of passing the exam.	2.97	.911	Serious
7. Examination stress and test anxiety.	3.02	.790	Serious
8. Lack of preparedness for the exam.	2.89	.949	Serious
9. Lack of study plan and strategy.	2.85	.957	Serious
10. Lack of exam management skills.	2.81	.930	Serious
11. Insufficiency of time to finish the exam.	2.40	.889	Moderately Serious
12. It is very expensive to review and to take the exam.	2.84	.821	Serious
13. Too many family and/or parental responsibilities.	2.61	.881	Serious
14. Suffering sickness or not feeling well on the duration of the examination.	2.64	.926	Serious
15. Lack of enough sleep prior to the examination days.	2.94	.882	Serious
16. Experiencing “mental block” during the examination due to nervousness.	2.96	.894	Serious
17. Poor physical environment of the examination venue.	2.64	.912	Serious
18. Availability of comfortable accommodation near the examination venue.	2.81	.846	Serious
Grand Mean	2.89	.593	Serious

Table 3. Degree of Seriousness of Problems Encountered in the CLE as Perceived by the Respondents

Legend: Very serious (3.26-4.00), Serious (2.51-3.25), Moderately serious (1.76-2.50), Less serious (1.00-1.75)

It can be inferred in table 4 that the perception of the respondents with regards to the problems encountered in preparing for and taking the CLE is serious as reflected in its grand mean of 2.89 (SD=.593).

It can be noted, that out of the 18 pre-identified problems, 17 of them were perceived by the respondents as serious. Meanwhile, the problem of “insufficiency of time to finish the exam” (M=2.40, SD=.889) was perceived as moderately serious. This is contrary to the study of Albina et al. (2022) which conveyed that the participants of their study did not agree that the time allotted to finish the exam is a challenge associated with taking the CLE.

Furthermore, these results are similar with those of Albina et al (2022), who discovered that six of the problems are perceived as challenges by the participants. These challenges were as follows: “(1) the exam is very difficult to answer, (2) some exam items were not discussed in school, (3) I was pressured by the personal and social consequences of failing the exam, (4) taking the exam is very expensive, (5) the language used in the exam is difficult to understand, and (6) I do not have

enough time to study or review.”

Regarding the respondents' perception that the CLE is very difficult to answer, this finding supports Pariñas and Obrero's (2012) study, which also revealed the difficulty encountered by their respondents in the various subjects in the CLE is high.

Furthermore, the findings of this study revealed that respondents perceived lack of familiarity with some of the words used in the exam items and experiencing mental block during the examination due to nervousness as serious problems encountered during the CLE. These findings support Pregoner's (2020) study, which discovered that mental factors were also a reason why participants in his study failed the licensure examination.

The current study's findings also indicated that reviewing and taking the exam is very costly, which respondents identified as a serious problem in preparing for and taking the licensure exam. According to the Asuncion (2019) study, respondents' problems with personal preparations, particularly financial aspects, are only moderately serious.

This present study shows that suffering sickness or not feeling well and lack of enough sleep prior to the examination days are serious problems as perceived by the respondents. This finding supports the study of Pregoner (2020), which likewise reported that most of the respondents with fever and cough during the time they take the exam, and those respondents with not enough sleep really affected their board examination performance in a negative way. This is supportive of the study of Briones and Romero (2020), which concluded that health is a big factor for one examinee, it is also important that they must observe their healthy diet on the

way to their examination day to make sure they are mentally, emotionally and physically prepared.

Regarding the respondents' perception that poor physical environment of the examination venue is a serious problem encountered in the CLE, this finding confirms to Pregoner (2020) study which also revealed that environmental factor affects the performance of examinees in the licensure examination. The respondents' performance in taking the board examination was hampered by excessive noise caused by an airplane near the examination venue and a chair that kept moving.

Correlation of the Extent of Influence of the Different Factors and the Degree of Seriousness of Problems Encountered in the CLE as Perceived by the Respondents

Factors in the CLE	Seriousness of Problems		
	Spearman's rho coefficient	p-value	Interpretation
Student factor	.271	.001	Significant
Home and Family factor	.203	.010	Significant
School factor	.195	.013	Significant
Review Center factor	.128	.106	Not Significant
Personal factor	.204	.009	Significant

Table 5: Correlation of the Extent of Influence of the Different Factors and the Degree of Seriousness of Problems Encountered in the CLE as Perceived by the Respondents

Spearman's rho test revealed that there is indeed a correlation between the seriousness of problems and four factors involved in this study namely: student factor ($\rho=.271$, $p=.001$), home and family factor ($\rho=.203$, $p=.010$), school factor ($\rho=.195$, $p=.013$) and personal factor ($\rho=.204$, $p=.009$), however, this correlation represents a small effect.

Regarding the correlation between personal factor and the problems encountered in the CLE, this finding lends support to the study of Badua (2020), which confirm that some students who are very good in their academic performance but have failed in the licensure examination due to personal problems, sickness and nervousness in the examination proper. Furthermore, in terms of the relationship between school factors and CLE problems, Espino et al. (2011) discovered a substantial significant positive relationship between academic and teaching performance.

Meanwhile, there is no significant correlation between the seriousness of problems and review center factor ($\rho=.128$, $p=.106$). Hence, there is no strong evidence to associate review center factor with the perceived problems encountered in the CLE. Similarly, Dayaday (2018), also concluded that review preparation has less significant effects on the performance of the passers and non-passers in the Electronics Engineering Board Examination.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the respondents perceived that all of the factors examined in this study, including student factor, home and family factor, school factor, review center factor, and personal factor, greatly affect the performance in Criminologist Licensure Examination. Furthermore, the respondents have similar perceptions in regards to the factors that influence the licensure examination. Meanwhile, respondents believe that preparing for and taking the CLE entails significant difficulties. Finally, the seriousness of the problems encountered in preparing and taking the CLE appears to be influenced by student, home and family, school, and personal factors, whereas the seriousness of the problems encountered in preparing and taking the CLE is not influenced by the review center factor. The findings of this study may be used to develop policies and programs to improve students' performance and success on the licensure examination.

VI. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings and conclusions, higher education institutions offering criminology programs should consider the various factors and problems discovered to have influenced CLE performance. This may help in the continuous review and enrichment of the B.S. Criminology curriculum to make it responsive and relevant to the needs of the time. As a result, it is

suggested that a well-established and regularly updated admissions and retention policy be considered and implemented. Furthermore, a qualified, competent, and dedicated faculty member may be assigned to handle professional and general education courses in the curriculum. In addition, the program may take into account the purchase, regular maintenance, and calibration of laboratory equipment and physical facilities required for B.S. Criminology program in accordance with CMO No.5 series of 2018.

Furthermore, it is recommended to incorporate any review course into the curriculum or facilitate any free review program, as not all B.S. graduates of criminology can afford to attend a review center to refresh their knowledge before taking the licensure examination. Meanwhile, faculty members may improve their teaching strategies and methodologies in order to promote effective learning through participation and attendance at training, seminars, workshops, and conferences. Furthermore, faculty members are encouraged to use a variety of instructional materials in order to ensure an effective teaching-learning process.

Finally, future researchers may conduct additional studies to add critical data and update this research. Future researchers could replicate the study and look at other variables and factors that may influence licensure examination performance, as the current study only focused on the five pre-identified factors. Similarly, further analysis of the problems encountered in preparing and taking the licensure examination is recommended in order to broaden the scope of understanding and shed more light on the problems encountered by criminology graduates in preparing and taking the CLE. Subsequently, qualitative research design using interviews among CLE passers and non-passers can be incorporated into future studies because combining qualitative and quantitative research designs can improve and enrich the results.

• DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST

The author claims that no known competing financial interests or personal relationships could have appeared to influence the results of this paper.

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